

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF THE DAMAGE AT THE TIP OF TUNNELLING CRACK IN GLASS FIBRE COMPOSITES

Ashish K. Bangaru^{1*}, Bent F. Sørensen¹ and Lars P. Mikkelsen¹

¹ Composite Mechanics and Structures, Department of Wind Energy,
Technical University of Denmark, Roskilde, Denmark
*akba@dtu.dk, bsqr@dtu.dk, lapm@dtu.dk

Keywords: Glass fibre composites, Fatigue, Tunnelling crack, X-ray tomography, Staining

ABSTRACT

The development of a distinct damage mode from the existing damage in composite laminates used in wind turbine blades is not fully understood; thus making it difficult to elucidate the event of chain of different failure mechanisms. In this paper, an experimental analysis was carried out on glass fibre composite laminate with the layup [0/60/0/-60]_s subjected to cyclic loading in order to document the damage subsequent to early stage of intralaminar matrix cracks, also referred as tunnelling cracks in off-axis plies 60°/-60°. The staining method coupled with X-ray Computed Tomography (CT) scan allowed in visualizing tunnelling crack propagation into the pure matrix region of 0° UD ply locally sandwiched between thin (60°) and thick (-60°) plies after 30,000 cycles. While close to the edge, due to edge effect phenomenon the tunnelling crack from the backing bundles resulted in considerable fibre breaks in 0° UD bundles.

1 INTRODUCTION

The typical lifetime of a wind turbine is around 20-30 years and during this period it experiences a high number of load cycles of the order of 10^8 - 10^9 . Unidirectional (UD) glass fibre composites made from non-crimp fabrics (NCF) constitutes the basic load carrying parts of a wind turbine blade. One of the major challenges when designing long blades is to consider fatigue of this material. Furthermore, damage progression under fatigue is a complex phenomenon because of many interacting damage modes at the micron-scale and it is very difficult to monitor these modes non-destructively. Therefore, it is of great interest to understand and describe the interaction of different damage mechanisms occurring on a micro-scale level.

Although 2D imaging methods such as SEM and camera imaging have been used to observe the damage progression on a micro-structural level, they are limited by the information on the surface; one does not really know how damage progresses inside the examined surface. Over the recent years, 3D X-ray Computed Tomography (CT) has been considered as one of the most promising technique to understand materials behaviour [1] with a high accuracy. In X-ray CT, the sample is placed between an X-ray source and a detector, the source emits X-rays through the sample on to the detector leaving a behind a projection image. The sample is rotated incrementally in fixed angles for each of which a projection image is acquired. With the help of a reconstruction algorithm, 3D image of the scanned volume is obtained. Owing to the differences in densities of the material constituents, the contrast appears in the projection images.

The latest X-ray systems provide micro- and even sub-micron resolution; also, they make it easier to carry out long multiple timescale studies. Till date only few works [2-6] exists that have shown the use of X-ray systems to study material damage at the micro-scale level. Yu et al. [4] used the staining technique to study matrix cracks and delamination in 3D woven carbon fibre composite specimen. This technique is effective only when all the damage modes are connected to the outer surfaces. It is because of this reason, long and wide test specimens were selected to take the advantage of edge effects.

In this study, the focus is on identifying damage resulting from the initial tunnelling cracks for the multidirectional laminate made up of glass fibre reinforced polymer. The approach adopted is the combination of staining and X-ray CT scanning to visualize damage in the selected regions supplemented with the information from white light imaging.

2 MATERIALS AND TESTING

2.1 Composite test specimen

The material examined for the project is glass fibre/epoxy composite system used in wind turbine blades. Figure 1 shows the fibre architecture used in the making of composite laminate represented as 0/b where ‘0’ corresponds to 0° UD layer and ‘b’ corresponds to thin backing layer with ±45°/90° orientations. The layup of the test laminate is [b/0/b/60/b/0/b/-60]_s where in ‘60’ and ‘-60’ corresponds to 0° UD layer oriented at 60° and -60° off-axis angles respectively. The composite plate was manufactured by vacuum assisted epoxy resin infusion process. From the composite plate, rectangular specimens with dimensions 400 mm x 80 mm were cut and tabs covering each 80 mm length were glued on both the ends. The specific geometry was selected in order to have as many off-axis cracks from the edges in the early stage of cyclic loading.

Figure 1: a) Front view image b) Back view image of the composite fibre architecture, and c) Layup configuration of the test laminate with dotted line as line of symmetry.

2.2 Fatigue test setup and testing

The test specimens were subjected to tension-tension cyclic loading on a hydraulic instron test machine with load control (sinusoidal waveform) and a stress ratio $R = 0.1$ at a frequency of 3 Hz. Applied maximum stress corresponds to 0.8% initial strain on the specimen. Figure 2 shows the test setup used for the testing. A white light was placed at the back to illuminate the specimen in order to visually detect the propagation of off-axis cracks through the images captured during the test using a digital camera. In the gauge region, two extensometers were attached to monitor the strain and subsequently stiffness degradation. The fatigue test was interrupted at 30,000 cycles for X-ray CT inspection to look up for damage evolution. For this purpose, small specimens of dimensions 50 mm x 4 mm were cut from the gauge region to have a good scan field of view that allows to capture small-scale details.

Figure 2: Fatigue testing set-up.

2.3 X-ray computed tomography

The small cut specimens were stained in zinc iodide and isopropyl alcohol solution for 48 hours prior to imaging on a Zeiss Xradia Versa 520 CT scanner. Small aluminium pin is glued at one end for each cut specimen to mount it easily on the specimen holder inside the scanner. Applied source voltage was 45 kV with high-resolution scan settings and an exposure time of 20 s for each scan projection. These scan settings were chosen in order to have a sufficient FoV to be able to clearly see damage regions. The final scanned composite volume was obtained from three overlapping scans along the sample length of 2.8 mm with a pixel size of 1.68 μm and a scan time of 68 hours.

Figure 3: X-ray CT scan set-up.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Damage detection through staining

During the initial stages of cyclic loading when the specimen is unloaded for ex-situ observations, there is a tendency for the closure of initiated cracks. Thus, making it difficult to visualize damage through scanned CT images. To enhance the visibility, staining method was used which has the advantage of high contrast relative to the bulk material. For the penetrant to flow through inside of the material the cracks needs to be joined from the specimen surface, in other words only connecting cracks are detected through this method. This attribute has been utilized to identify the underlying damage modes subsequent to the tunnelling cracks.

3.2 Damage distribution in the neighboring ply

The tunneling cracks from the thick off-axis -60° layer tend to propagate locally into the spaces of matrix rich region in the 0° UD ply resulting in pure matrix cracking. These cracks were found to be discontinuous meaning that the UD bundles in between interrupt them. 1 of 1000 projections were obtained through the thickness to uncover the effect of tunneling cracks inside from the surface.

Figure 4: Full stitch scan image.

Figure 4 shows a full stitch scan from the three scan regions focussed on the sub-laminate [0/-60/-60/0] of the total layup configuration. Scanning through all the projection images revealed that the backing fibres of 0° UD layer intermittently shield the tunnelling cracks. As can be observed in figure 5a, 5b the tip of the crack stops at the backing fibre, this could be attributed to the reason that the specimen is still in the early stages of fatigue life i.e., subjected to low number of load cycles.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 5: Tunneling crack a) stopping at the backing fibre bundles b) crossing over single backing fibre and c) penetrating into pure matrix region

It is also observed that the tunneling crack does not penetrate into the matrix on the opposite side of the 0° UD ply (Figure 5a, 5b, 5c), this can be explained from the fact the amount of matrix is more or less uniform throughout the specimen under study.

Furthermore, it would be interesting to study how these partially grown matrix cracks from the tunneling cracks would behave at higher number of load cycles and this is currently an ongoing work.

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, X-ray CT imaging was used to characterize early stage fatigue damage progression in multidirectional laminate made from glass fibre composites. The staining technique proves to be one of the effective way in visualizing tunnelling cracks and also to detect other damage resulting from these cracks. The tip of the tunnelling crack finds its way to propagate into matrix rich region causing pure matrix cracking. In case of presence of backing fibres, the tip of tunnelling crack abruptly stops close to the proximity of fibres. With increasing number of load cycles, it would be interesting to know the severity of these cracks; delaminations or fibre bundle breaks.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author would like to thank the technicians from Fibrelab and Mechanical testing lab for sample preparation and set-up of testing apparatus. The author is grateful to the financial support from CASMaT (Center for Advanced Structural and Material Testing) of Denmark Technical University (DTU). The present work carried out is a part of the collaborative project titled “Understanding fatigue through multi-scale testing and modelling” between DTU Civil, DTU Mechanical and DTU Wind Energy departments. The primary goal of this project is to study the fatigue damage at three length scales – micro, macro and structural level.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. F. Manwell, J. G. McGowan and A. L. Rogers, *Wind turbine materials and components, Wind energy explained: theory, design and application*, 2nd edition, John Wiley and Sons, Chichester, 2010.
- [2] F. Sket, R. Seltzer, J.M. Molina-Aldareguía, C. Gonzalez, J. LLorca, Determination of damage micromechanisms and fracture resistance of glassfiber/epoxycross-ply laminate by means of X-ray computed microtomography, *Compos.Sci. Technol.* 72 (2) (2012).
- [3] J. Schilling, B.P.R. Karedla, A.K. Tatiparthi, M.A. Verges, P.D. Herrington, X-ray computed microtomography of internal damage infiber reinforced polymer matrix composites, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 65 (14) (2005).
- [4] Yu, R. Blanc, C. Soutis, P.J. Withers, Evolution of damage during the fatigue of 3D woven glass-fibre reinforced composites subjected to tension tension loading observed by time-lapse X-ray tomography, *Compos. Part A* 82 (2016).
- [5] B. Yu, R.S. Bradley, C. Soutis, P.J. Hogg, P.J. Withers, 2D and 3D imaging of fatigue failure mechanisms of 3D woven composites, *Compos. Sci. Technol.* 77(2015).
- [6] S. Topal, L. Baiocchi, A.D. Crocombe, S.L. Ogin, P. Potluri, P.J. Withers, M. Quaresimin, P.A. Smith, M.C. Poole, A.E. Bogdanovich, Late-stage fatigue damage in a 3D orthogonal non-crimp woven composite: an experimental and numerical study, *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.* 79 (2015).